

Additional File 2. Culture media used for growing cells.

mKSCs, mMSCs, RAW macrophages, hBM-MSCs:	Dulbecco's Modified Eagle's Medium (DMEM, D6546, Sigma), 10% Foetal Calf Serum (FCS), 2 mM L-Glutamine.
hKCs:	DMEM/F12 (12-719Q, Lonza), 5% FCS, epidermal growth factor (10 ng/ml), hydrocortisone (36 ng/ml) 3,3',5-Triiodo-L-thyronine sodium salt (4 pg/ml), insulin-transferrin-selenium liquid medium (1x).
hUC-MSCs:	Minimum Essential Medium (Life Technologies 32561037), 10% FCS, 5 ng/mL recombinant human basic Fibroblast Growth Factor.